

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF INTERNATIONAL TOURNAMENTS AL-KHAKIM AT-TERMIZI IN THE EDUCATION OF YOUTH STUDENTS.

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Annotation: *This article contains information about the attention of the state and the government to the national sport of wrestling, the role and importance of international tournaments Al-Hakim at-Termizi in the education of the younger generation and schoolchildren.*

Keywords: *international, memory, turner, arena, federation, International Wrestling Association, championship, Asia.*

One of our great writers said it was good to go back to Mozi and build a business. After all, when we remember the good deeds of past years, a strange light wakes up in the heart. Here I want to tell about the history of our national wrestling, its endless development in the years after independence, and also to recognize that this ancient sport is becoming a passion for millions of people around the world. It is obvious to everyone that after Uzbekistan gained independence, there was a real upsurge in the development of wrestling, which is our national sport. In order to spread it more widely among the population, large-scale wrestling tournaments were held in a number of regions of our republic.

In 1992, at the initiative of the first President, the issue of the health of the nation was made an urgent task. Our President mobilized physical culture and sports organizations, officials and specialists to promote the mass development of all sports in order to improve the health of young people, and pay special attention to our national sport.

Since 1992 wrestling competitions and tournaments have been widely held in the regions. For example, every two years international tournaments of Pakhlavon Mahmud in Khorezm, Tursun of Yusupov's father in Bukhara, Allam Bahauddin Naqshband, Amir Temur in Shakhrisabz, Al-Khakim At-Termizi in Termez are held. In the history of national wrestling, there is a document written in golden letters that gave potential and strength to wrestling in our region. It is known that in 1993 a resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers was announced. This document, signed by the first President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, marked the beginning of an international tournament dedicated to the memory of Al-Hakim At-Tirmizi for the prize of our President every two years in our region. The fourth international tournament dedicated to the memory of our great-grandfather, held in 1999, was declared the Asian Open Championship on the initiative of the International Wrestling Association.

At the start of this international tournament, the raising of the national flag to the anthem of Uzbekistan in the Surkhan oasis, a remote region of Uzbekistan where wrestling lovers from all over the world gather, is a clear proof of the upbringing of the youth of this oasis in the spirit of patriotism.

At the beginning of each tournament, the wrestling enthusiasts who filled the stadium and the best wrestlers in the world who came from all over the world could not hide their excitement and took to the field under the flag of each country. me to grow up as a child of the level of a physically perfect person ”positively affects the development of boys and girls who will be shields for each other.

Both the judges and a large number of fans followed the performances of each of the wrestlers at each of the international tournaments with great attention. The fact that the fights between the wrestlers were sharp and uncompromising in duels will be remembered as if it were yesterday.

Each international tour guarantees the discovery of new fans. Our friends who won the absolute mass of competitions in the international tournament dedicated to

the memory of Al-Hakim At-Tirmidhi 1st turner (1993) in absolute weight Ural Toraev (Surkhandarya region); Rustam Ergashev (Surkhandarya region) won the 2nd tournament (1995) in open weight. Erali Makhmarasulov (Surkhandarya region) won the 3rd tournament (1997) in open weight; Toshtemir Muhammadiev (Surkhandarya region) won the 4th tournament (1999) in absolute weight; 5-10 turners (2001, 2003, 2005, 2007, 2009, 2011) in absolute weight Abdulla Tangriev (Surkhandarya region); Samijon Ubaidulloev won the 11th tournament (2013) in open weight; (Surkhandarya); Samijon Ubaidulloev won the 14th tournament (2015) in open weight; (Surkhandarya); Abdulla Kholirov (Surkhandarya region) won the 15th tournament (2017) in open weight. Boltaboy Boltaev (Khorezm) won the 16th tournament (2019) in open weight; In the 17th tournament (2021), wrestlers such as Mukhsin Khisomiddinov (Surkhandarya region) won, leaving the rest of the world behind.

We will not remember a single tournament held in our country, warm and bright memories will wake up in our hearts. Each tournament is an event worth reading. I must admit that the memorable moments were full of fights that showed amazing human strength. For example, the co-hosting of the 10th International Tournament and the 8th World Wrestling Championship in 2011, the active participation of wrestlers from more than 30 countries and wrestlers from more than 20 countries in the competition is a sign of the increasing prestige of the tournament.

If we look at the list of wrestlers who participated in international tournaments dedicated to the memory of our great-grandfather Al-Hakim At-Tirmizi, we will see that our national wrestling has covered almost the entire world. For example, the participation of wrestlers from distant New Zealand, Brazil, Japan, South Korea and many other Asian countries in the tournament in Termez speaks volumes. The wrestling tournament held in Termez is, so to speak, a lesson for thousands of our young people, and secondly, our young fans get the necessary experience from these wrestling seconds.

If you watch international gymnasts, then over the years of independence, the number of people interested in national wrestling and directly involved in this sport has increased not many times, but sharply. Ultimately, this will contribute to the health of the nation. The third factor that comes out of these wrestling tournaments is that the people, the nation, recognize their kata wrestlers. In these fights, victories in the absolute weight category Orol Torayev, Rustam Ergashev, Erali Makhmarasulov, Toshtemir Muhammadiev, Abdullo Tangriev, Samijon Ubaidulloev, Abdullo Kholiarov, Boltaboy Boltaev, Mukhsin Khisomiddinov and many other wrestlers became famous.

Of great importance in the upbringing of the younger generation of many wrestling countries is the holding every two years in our region of the "International Tournament in memory of al-Hakim At-Termizi" in memory of our great-grandfather for the prize of our president. our region and our republic. In the public education system of our country, the teaching of wrestling in the program of physical education for schoolchildren and in these lessons to acquaint young people with the legendary heroes of our struggle and promote our struggle, to educate schoolchildren to be patriotic, courageous and courageous serves as an important tool in the development of flowers.

Since the foundation of the championships of Uzbekistan, Asia and the world in wrestling was laid in this country, every schoolchild and the younger generation should grow up after their grandparents. After all, it is inevitable that a generation that has grown up with an understanding of its past will have its place and its word in the future.

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